

Deliverable D14.1

Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

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1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis – the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (Blueprint, for short). This document is the second version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Roadmap (Roadmap, for short), presenting an updated overview of the steps needed to arrive at the Blueprint that meets requirements from the project use cases, referred to as Drivers, and is viable for TRE providers (referred to Providers).

The first version of the Roadmap consisted of three phases, with Phase 1 (in 2024) leading to the first version of the Blueprint. The current report summarizes the results of Phase 1, which includes the first version of the Blueprint and accompanying first version training material and a machine-readable catalogue of TREs, validation reports from the Drivers and Providers, the first version Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting infrastructure (AAAI) blueprint report, and first deployable demonstrator report. Furthermore, the report summarizes ongoing developments within the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and other relevant efforts related to federated analyses of sensitive data within Europe.

Based on the results from Phase 1, we propose continuing with Phase 2 and Phase 3 of the Roadmap as planned. Specifically, in Phase 2 (Co-creation and Validation), we will extend the Blueprint with operating procedures and interface definitions, while addressing the gaps and additional requirements identified by the Drivers in their analysis of the first version of the Blueprint. In Phase 3 (Maturity and Continuity), we will release the final version of the Blueprint. Importantly, Phase 1 has seen a high level of engagement and excitement across the project work packages, which has been essential in developing and aligning the first version of the Blueprint to Driver requirements and Provider capabilities. We will therefore continue our planned series of yearly workshops focused on requirements and capabilities (May) and evaluation and adoption (September).

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures	No

<p>framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)</p>	
	<p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
	<p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).</p>	<p>No</p>

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.

4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)

3. Methods

3.1. Deliverable scope and methodology

The D14.1 deliverable is the updated version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Roadmap document presenting the steps needed to develop the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint for building an interoperable network of TRE services. This updated roadmap outlines the second phase in the Roadmap for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. This update is based on a review of the results from the first phase of the Blueprint roadmap and ongoing developments within the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and other relevant efforts related to federated analyses of sensitive data within Europe.

4. Description of work accomplished

The following two sections describe the developments within the first year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project. Internal developments correspond to the first phase in the Draft Roadmap for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint², while external developments reflect those of related projects relevant for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Internal developments include the first versions of the EOSC-ENTRUST Architecture blueprint, Driver validation report, Provider adoption and evaluation report, AAAI report, and Workflows report. External developments include those within the EOSC federation, EHDS and the TEHDAS2 project, EOSC-ENTRUST's sister projects TITAN and SIESTA, the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI), DARE-UK, the EGI TRE work group, and the Swiss TREs in BioMedIT.

4.1 Summary of EOSC-ENTRUST first year developments

4.1.1 Architecture blueprint

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 13.4 (D13.4), Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework³ (hereafter the Blueprint), and its companion Deliverable 13.2

² <https://zenodo.org/records/12703951>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>

(D13.2), Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework⁴, were released 10th of December 2024. The Blueprint presented a draft architecture specification, which were built on analyses of the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint⁵ and its mapping to selected ENTRUST TRE providers and the four ENTRUST use case projects (hereafter Drivers).

The mapping of TRE providers focused on identifying matches and gaps between the DARE UK Blueprint infrastructure layer and each TRE's architecture (Table 5.2.2 in D13.4). Whereas most TRE-level services in the DARE UK Blueprint mapped to corresponding architecture components in all the ENTRUST TREs, federation-related services were only mapped to a few TREs or not mapped at all. Importantly, the mapping also identified a mismatch between the DARE UK Blueprint and how the mapped ENTRUST TREs allow project principal investigators (PI) to control input and output to their TRE project environments.

The Driver mapping focused on mapping each Driver's data usage patterns and interoperability-related requirements against the DARE UK Data Space Model and infrastructure layer. The mappings (Table 5.3.1 in D13.4) identified five services that were required by two to four Drivers to be missing from the DARE UK Blueprint: Data access requests, Safe user training and certification, General user training, Pseudonymisation, and Data publishing (FAIR).

The Year one ENTRUST infrastructure architecture was built on the DARE UK Blueprint to address the initial gaps identified by the Provider and Driver mappings. Important extensions include expanded Federation Services, specialized Secure Data Archives for publishing datasets, and Project environments where PIs take the roles as Input and Output Approver. Future versions of the Blueprint will also provide operating procedures, interface definitions, and template agreements for the federation.

4.1.2 Driver validation report

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1), Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis⁶, was released 7th of March 2025. The report describes how the Drivers validated the Blueprint, by providing their updated requirements, describing four specific use cases and a generic user journey that the Blueprint should support, and reporting a gap analysis between Driver requirements and the Blueprint.

The Drivers established an initial list of requirements as a milestone report (M7.1), which formed the basis for the Year one version of the Blueprint. The updated requirements (Appendix 2 in D7.1) were refined to provide functional implementation-agnostic

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/14361989>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/14988869>

descriptions, prioritized by each Driver according to the MoSCoW method, and mapped to the SATRE⁷ framework. In this way, they clearly state the interoperability needs of the Drivers in terms of their requirements to a federated network of TREs.

The Drivers described the following four use cases for the Blueprint: (1) calling individual genetic variants from data residing in separate TREs, (2) determine if teacher bias is associated with math achievement in primary schools based on data from 3 European countries, (3) meta-analysis of individual participant data from multiple clinical trials, with data residing in different repositories or TREs, and (4) creating synthetic data instances that are representative and useful for method (AI) development without revealing personal data.

Based on these four use cases and additional analyses by each Driver, the report describes a generic user journey for data analyses across multiple TREs. The journey consists of six steps, one of which is optional: Data Discovery, Data Access Application, User Training and Certification, Data Preparation and Provision (optional), Data Analysis, and Results Output. These steps, which include several additional substeps involving Blueprint actors with distinct roles, align closely with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) user journey⁸.

The Drivers' gap analysis of the Blueprint identified 16 gaps between the updated Driver requirements and the Blueprint (Table 3 in D7.1). Moreover, the gap analysis identified additional Driver requirements to the Discovery Service, AAI, User Training, Software Service, and Disclosure Control components in the Blueprint. Finally, the report recommended focusing on the following key areas for the next version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint: (1) establish a governance structure for the federation, (2) provide a central access point for user registration and other federation-level user processes, (3) publish and use standardized terminology, (4) adopt a metadata standard, (5) develop a unified data access request procedure, (6) include user support services and comprehensive training programs, (7) align architecture components, standards, and processes with ongoing EHDS and EOSC developments.

4.1.3 Provider adoption and evaluation report

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 10.1 (D10.1), Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 1 blueprint and technology, including barriers to adoption & TRE gap analysis⁹, was released 7th April 2025. The report describes key achievements in coordinating and mapping the ENTRUST TRE providers (hereafter Providers), including establishing and running the TRE

⁷ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁸

<https://tehdas.eu/tehdas1/results/tehdas-identifies-user-journey-for-cross-border-health-data-sharing/>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15166675>

Provider Forum, developing an initial TRE Inventory, assessing baseline capabilities and gaps, and developing a dynamic requirements management framework.

The Year one TRE Provider Forum consisted of 17 founding member organisations from 15 European countries, where some represented multiple TREs. The Provider Forum is run through bi-weekly meetings with a set agenda. Among other things, it aims to establish a sustainable community beyond the ENTRUST project. Towards this end, the Provider Forum is aiming for a centrally organized structure that is open to TREs at varying maturity levels.

The TRE Inventory was based on a survey of the TRE members of the Provider Forum and gathered data on their capabilities, governance, security measures, and maturity levels. This data formed the basis for the contents of the First Edition of the Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue¹⁰ and provided critical inputs to the TRE baseline capabilities and gap analysis.

The gap analysis identified interoperability, training and standardisation, and data compliance as key challenges for integrating current TREs. Challenges in interoperability involve both diverse legal and organisational frameworks and lack of technical standards, such as authentication methods. Challenges in training and standardisation involve lack of standardised training and certification of TRE users, including both general training, such as information governance and ethics of sensitive data analysis, and specific training on individual TRE solutions. Challenges in data compliance involve lack of a common minimum standard for TREs and information security; instead, TREs are focused on satisfying local legislations and concerns. Addressing these challenges is necessary for integrating current and future TREs into an interoperable European framework and will require continued effort from Provider forum members and other stakeholders.

Development of the requirements management framework focused on identifying core functional criteria for the requirement management framework itself and ensuring that these align with the needs of both Drivers and Providers. Moving forward, particular attention will be given to addressing the diverse requirements of Drivers from different domains.

4.1.4 AAI report

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 16.1 (D16.1) The AAI for TREs Blueprint, first version¹¹, was released 11th March 2025. The report presents the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAI) Blueprint for TREs, a critical component designed to complement the broader TRE architecture by addressing the unique challenges of managing sensitive data, especially controlling access to them.

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14412490>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15006945>

The current landscape of TREs is fragmented, with researchers encountering a multitude of disparate systems and providers struggling with incompatible technology and governance frameworks. The AAI Blueprint therefore builds upon the established AARC Blueprint Architecture and its guidelines. However, the complex requirements of TREs mean targeted enhancements are necessary. Specifically, the blueprint extends the traditional AARC framework through four key improvements:

1. Account Creation: Secure and efficient processes for provisioning user identities that are tailored to the operational context of TREs.
2. Identity Vetting: Rigorous verification methods that ensure users are who they claim to be, thereby facilitating reliable access across national borders.
3. Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC): A fine-grained authorisation model that evaluates not only the conventional subject, object, and operation but also the surrounding environment, thereby centralizing and standardizing policy decisions.
4. Accounting Layer: An advanced framework for monitoring, auditing, and tracking usage, which is essential for identifying and responding to potential violations or unauthorized access.

These enhancements are the direct result of a detailed analysis of TRE requirements, which also included and addressed heightened security needs, improved interoperability, and stringent accountability. The outcome is a comprehensive set of requirements and recommendations that any AAI implementation must fulfill, ensuring that the security infrastructure is both robust and adaptable to the evolving landscape of sensitive data management.

4.1.5 Workflows report

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 19.1 (D19.1), Deployable Demonstrators of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments¹², was released 12th December 2024. The report describes an installable demonstrator of federated sensitive data discovery, built from open source and standards-based components. Specifically, the report outlines key achievements that include the latest release of the Workflow Execution Service (WfExS) backend¹³ and a demonstration of how WfExS, combined with a TRE-specific job submission system, can allow TREs to participate in two federated data discovery networks, a comprehensive gap analysis that identified necessary WfExS-backend changes and extensions, and a target design for the next WfExS version.

The WfExS-backend is a high-level workflow orchestrator designed for container-based workflow execution in secure (and other) computing environments. Key WfExS features include workflow execution management, data and execution provenance and tracking,

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/14412863>

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15308101>

support for the Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH)'s standardized data repository and software tool registry services, compute backend flexibility, and computational resource management. WfExS has adopted and processes workflows according to the GA4GH Workflow Execution Service (WES) standard. In the TRE demonstrator, based on the TRE-FX stack from the TRE-FX project¹⁴, WfExS receives workflow submissions through an external Submission Layer. An internal TRE Controller polls the Submission Layer for new job submissions and submits these to a Workflow Execution Layer running the WfExS-backend. The report provides two distinct data discovery workflows that, along with the complete TRE-FX stack, were installed and tested on two different sites.

The gap analysis of the demonstrator identified several gaps related to deployment, user interface, TRE air gapping, use of and Research Object Crates (RO-Crates) for provenance (Table 6 in D19.1). The demonstrator work and gap analysis led to several extensions in the WfExS-backend, released as WfExS-backend version 1.0¹⁵.

Finally, based on the lessons learned from the Year one demonstrator work and an analysis of the first version of the Blueprint architecture, the D19.1 report describes a target architecture for the next demonstrator release. The report further mapped the components of this proposed architecture to components of the Blueprint architecture, identifying two components related to support for intermediary storage and a minimal disclosure procedure to be missing from the Year one version of the Blueprint.

4.2 External developments

4.2.1 EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹⁶ is one of the main initiatives contributing to the European strategy for data¹⁷ keeping Europe at the forefront of Open Science by enabling the Web of FAIR data and Services, and supporting the discovery, access and reuse of research outputs within the European Research Area (ERA)¹⁸. The evolution of EOSC is guided through the Strategic Research and Innovations Agenda (SRIA) and Multi Annual Roadmaps (MAR)¹⁹. In the last decade, many organisations within the research and education domain, at national and European level, have contributed to the development of EOSC.

¹⁴ <https://trefx.uk/>

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/13821549>

¹⁶ <https://eosc.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066>

¹⁸

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en

¹⁹ <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>

Establishing the EOSC Federation

During the first year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, EOSC launched its next phase involving the build-up of the EOSC Federation²⁰. To start establishing the EOSC Federation, the European Commission acquired the first node²¹ of the EOSC Federation through a tender procedure²². This node was launched during the EOSC Symposium 2024²³, on 21 - 23rd October 2024, in Berlin, Germany. One node does however not make a federation, so the EOSC Tripartite started the procedure to select the subsequent nodes to build the EOSC Federation during the summer of 2024. In February 2025, the selection procedure was finalised and 13 nodes were selected to join the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation. From 17th to 18th March 2025, the European Commission hosted the kick-off meeting for the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation²⁴, marking the launch of the EOSC Federation. Here, representatives of all 13 nodes plus the EC EOSC Node came together to discuss and plan the cross-node collaborations. Multiple nodes proposed use cases on supporting the handling of sensitive data within the EOSC Federation.

The aim of the first wave of the build-up phase is to establish the first nodes capable of joining the Federation, and to enable cross-node use cases to be demonstrated at the EOSC Symposium 2025, 3rd-5th November 2025, in Brussels, Belgium²⁵.

The EOSC Federation Handbook

To support organisations interested in joining the EOSC Federation as a node and/or to onboard services, resources and/or research output through a node into the federation, the EOSC Association took the initiative to develop the EOSC Federation Handbook^{26,27}. The EOSC Federation Handbook aims to be a practical guideline for organisations that are interested in making their resources available within and across the EOSC Federation. It has been written through a community-wide collaboration with open consultations, meetings, events and sprints. Inspiration was taken from the ELIXIR Handbook of Operations²⁸, which was used to define the outline of the EOSC Federation Handbook. The EOSC Federation Handbook will be tested and updated during the build-up phase of the federation.

EOSC-ENTRUST Network of Trusted Research Environments

²⁰ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/>

²¹ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

²² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-announces-winners-eosc-procurement>

²³ <https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/>

²⁴ <https://eosc.eu/news/2025/04/the-eosc-federations-build-up-phase-is-underway/>

²⁵ <https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-symposium-2025/>

²⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

²⁷ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

²⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>

During the second year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, the EOSC Federation will be established. Four partners of the EOSC-ENTRUST project (i.e. CSC, ELIXIR, EUDAT, SURF) participate in the build-up phase as members of the first nodes joining the federation. As providing services capable of handling sensitive data has been identified as one of the topics for the build-up phase, EOSC-ENTRUST needs to develop an approach on how TREs are onboarded to the EOSC Federation, for example:

- EOSC-ENTRUST can establish a node offering TRE capabilities and join the EOSC Federation as a node
- The network of TREs can be onboarded to an existing EOSC node and offer the network of TREs through the EOSC node
- Organisations offering a TRE can onboard the TRE individually into an EOSC node of choice

Depending on the approach, this should be included in the EOSC-ENTRUST roadmap.

4.2.2 EHDS and TEHDAS2

The European Health Data Space regulation²⁹ was published in the EU Official Journal on 5th March 2025 and took effect on 25th March 2025. Regulation (EU) 2025/327 adopted on 11th February 2025, establishes the European Health Data Space (EHDS) to enhance individual access to and control over their personal electronic health data within the EU. It also aims to facilitate the use of such data for broader societal benefits, including research, innovation, policymaking, and health threat preparedness.

The EHDS regulation set in place requirements for digital business capabilities for future Health Data Access Bodies, that include similar capabilities to those in scope of EOSC-ENTRUST, such as SPE (TRE/RAZ) and a catalogue of SPEs.

The second Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS2) prepares the ground for the harmonised implementation of the secondary use of health data in EHDS³⁰. TEHDAS2 will contribute to a harmonised implementation of the EHDS Regulation through concrete guidelines and technical specifications. Some of these documents and resources will also provide input to implementing acts of the regulation. Hence, the joint action will increase the preparedness for the EHDS implementation and lead to better coordination of Member State joint efforts towards the secondary use of health data, while also reducing fragmentation in policies and practices related to secondary use.

²⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2025/327>

³⁰ <https://tehdas.eu/>

TEHDAS2 WP7 will release guidelines and technical specifications about Secure Processing Environments and also define common security requirements applicable to all SPEs and specify functional and technical services to ensure interoperability. The list of SPE Requirements will be released for public consultation in September 2025.

4.2.3 EOSC-TITAN and EOSC-SIESTA

EOSC-TITAN³¹ and EOSC-SIESTA³² are sister projects to EOSC-ENTRUST, funded by the same Horizon Europe INFRA-EOSC EU³³ programme.

4.2.3.1 EOSC-TITAN

The EOSC-TITAN project aims to develop secure and trustworthy confidential data processing and sharing capabilities. The project emphasizes privacy preservation and AI technological solutions, ensuring compliance with existing ethical, regulatory, and legal EU boundaries. The approach of EOSC-TITAN aligns with the FAIR principles, promoting the sharing of sensitive data in a secure manner. The project focuses on two primary use cases: government data and healthcare. Like EOSC-ENTRUST, EOSC-TITAN is under the umbrella of the EOSC ecosystem. This collaborative environment enhances the project's ability to develop and demonstrate its open-source software platform effectively.

To ensure community adoption, EOSC-TITAN will demonstrate its solutions in several vertical cross-border scenarios, particularly in the public administration and healthcare sectors. These demonstrations aim to showcase the practical applications and benefits of EOSC-TITAN's software artifacts, encouraging widespread adoption and integration within the EOSC framework³⁴.

4.2.3.2 EOSC-SIESTA

EOSC-SIESTA aims to design and build Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics in the European Open Science Cloud ecosystem. The overall objective of EOSC-SIESTA is to enhance the EOSC Exchange services by delivering a set of cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC, thereby demonstrating the feasibility of applying FAIR principles to such data. Providing access to sensitive or confidential data while preserving privacy, confidentiality and usability for researchers is still a challenge. Existing solutions like safe rooms, safe pods, or data safe havens often hinder the development of reproducible research and seem counterintuitive when dealing with open science and FAIR principles.

³¹ <https://titan-eosc.eu/>

³² <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/siesta/>

³³ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-research-infrastructures_en

³⁴ <https://titan-eosc.eu/about/>

EOSC-SIESTA envisions a set of tools, services, and methodologies to facilitate effective sharing of sensitive data in the EOSC: By adopting a cloud-based model, the project aims to promote the uptake of sensitive data sharing and processing. The project will deliver trusted cloud-based environments for the management and sharing of sensitive data that are built in a reproducible way, together with a set of services and tools to ease the secure sharing of sensitive data in the EOSC through state-of-the-art anonymization techniques.

4.2.4 Other initiatives

4.2.4.1 GDI

The Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)³⁵ project launched in November 2022, with participants from 70 institutes across 24 European countries and 2 international organisations. The four year project's mission is to provide access to genomic data to improve research, policy making and healthcare across Europe, thereby supporting the 1+Million Genomes (1+MG)³⁶ initiative.

GDI builds on the Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG)³⁷ project outputs, aiming to establish *a federated, sustainable and secure data infrastructure open community standards to access genomic and related phenotypic and clinical data across Europe*. Secure data infrastructure and federated access are also main goals for EOSC-ENTRUST, with GDI being one of its driver projects, so alignment is critical. Collaboration between the two projects will ensure that the federated human genomics infrastructure established by GDI aligns with the broader TRE framework being developed by EOSC-ENTRUST. GDI also has close ties to the Genome of Europe (GoE) project, which launched in February 2025. The two projects have signed a Memorandum of Understanding and the aim is to make GoE data available to the GDI infrastructure.

During the first half of the project duration, GDI achieved significant outputs, such as releasing the first edition of the GDI Starter Kit³⁸ for cross-border access to genomic and phenotypic data. Moreover, GDI released two public videos demonstrating the GDI technical infrastructure in the examples of “Accessing colorectal cancer data” and “Allele lookup in severe COVID-19 cases” using distributed real-like synthetic data³⁹. These examples are closely related to the EOSC-ENTRUST Driver 1 use cases. Now, in the second

³⁵ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

³⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

³⁷ <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

³⁸ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure>

³⁹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/gdi-technical-infrastructure>

half of the GDI project, the final features to be implemented before the project's closure in October 2026 are being defined.

4.2.4.2 Simpl

Simpl⁴⁰ is an open-source, intelligent and secure middleware platform designed to facilitate data access and interoperability across European data spaces. It plays a pivotal role in establishing Common European Data Spaces⁴¹ - data ecosystems where participants can safely and securely share data. Simpl empowers data providers with complete control over data access within these ecosystems.

The primary goal of Simpl is to develop a large-scale modular and interoperable open-source European cloud-to-edge middleware platform. This platform will integrate data infrastructures and services to meet the diverse needs of various data spaces and support the implementation of the European Cloud Federation. The middleware will utilise existing building blocks as much as possible and serve as an enabling layer for the interconnection of the various data spaces, public authority cloud resources, artificial intelligence ecosystems etc., by providing the required interoperability mechanisms.

Simpl⁴² is guided by the following five principles:

1. Anchored to specific use cases: the data sets and their infrastructure should be seamlessly interconnected and made interoperable.
2. Smart and modular: allow the replacement or addition of components without affecting the rest of the system.
3. Open source: publicly accessible, and allow anyone to see, modify and distribute it.
4. Green, scalable and agile: allow monitoring of its environmental performance, and the addition of new users without affecting performance.
5. Secure and interoperable: ensure trust, confidence and compliance with regulations are built into the system, enabling data to flow across multiple providers and Member States.

The initial schedule for release of the first version of Simpl was at the end of year 2024, but the project release has been delayed.

4.2.4.3 TREs in Switzerland

In Switzerland, three major research institutions (ETH Zurich, University of Basel and University of Lausanne/Swiss Bioinformatics Institute) and their TREs have established

⁴⁰ <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/>

⁴¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

⁴² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl>

BioMedIT as a federated secure platform for sensitive data research⁴³. Their report ‘Versatile Trusted Research Environments – An Approach for Switzerland’⁴⁴ outlines the Swiss approach to TREs, which is characterised by its versatile and federated nature, thereby allowing for high adaptability and complementarity across institutions.

The report highlights that building and ensuring trust with the full set of stakeholders may be the most important part of delivering a TRE network, beyond technical considerations. Further, it describes data, people, technology and processes as the four main pillars of a safe and effective TRE. The Swiss model is built around four interrelated layers: infrastructure at the base, research platforms at the operational core, researcher engagement at the user level, and coordination functions that span all layers to ensure cohesion and efficiency.

Switzerland has four types of platforms for handling sensitive data: single purpose TREs, local processing, secure cloud infrastructure and versatile TREs. The report discusses these four types, and concludes that versatile federated TREs offer significant advantages over standalone systems for researchers. They are able to evolve with user needs for research purposes. They further encourage collaboration across institutions, enabling researchers to work with diverse datasets without physically transferring them—thus reducing data exposure risks. Federation also supports standardisation of security, compliance, and governance practices across the network, improving trust among stakeholders. Additionally, shared investment in infrastructure and expertise leads to greater cost efficiency and sustainability.

The BioMedIT report stresses that TREs should be usable for researchers - to ensure that they are used, co-developed along research and data providing organisations, federated and not duplicated and fully coordinated across the full stack, though this requires a high degree of trust and openness among organisations in a federation.

4.2.4.4 EGI Landscape report - Trusted Research Environments

The European Grid Infrastructure (EGI) is a federation of computing and storage resource providers united by a mission to support research and development⁴⁵. Within the EGI, a work group for TREs has been reviewing the TRE landscape since 2023 and present their findings in the ‘TRE Landscape report’⁴⁶. This report describes a diverse landscape of European TREs and highlights their role in facilitating secure and compliant research involving sensitive data. In short, the report provides:

⁴³ <https://www.biomedit.ch/>

⁴⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/14012894>

⁴⁵ <https://www.egi.eu>

⁴⁶

https://documents.egi.eu/public/RetrieveFile?docid=4169&filename=EGI_TRE_WG_Landscape_Report_2024-10-25.pdf&version=2

- Definitions of TREs, with three real-life implementations illustrating how these support secure data handling and analysis
- Technical requirements for TREs, including data security and privacy, compliance with regulations, usability and accessibility for researchers and scalability and adaptability to various research needs.
- Challenges and approaches for achieving interoperability between TREs, illustrated by three different operational modes of TREs: institutional/self-hosted, private cloud and federation. It does not, however, provide examples of TREs operating in the respective modes.
- An exploration of the use of emerging technologies such as Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)⁴⁷, Constellation⁴⁸, homomorphic computing⁴⁹ and synthetic data usage in enhancing the capabilities of TREs
- Scenarios for integrating TREs with the EGI services, through on demand deployment, EGI Federated Cloud based TRE and integration with EOSC nodes.

The EGI TRE Landscape report lastly concludes that the demand for TREs is growing, therefore TRE deployment and adoption must be accelerated, that interconnecting TREs is an emerging challenge, therefore operational, business and governance models for interconnected TRE ecosystems must be found and that vocabularies and standards to facilitate uptake of TREs in different sectors must be identified.

5. Results

The first year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project focused on laying the foundational elements for a European network for TREs, resulting in the Year one version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint (D13.4)⁵⁰. This initial blueprint was developed through a process of analysis and mapping of the DARE UK Federated Architecture⁵¹ against selected TRE providers and the project's use cases, referred to as Drivers. The work accomplished in this phase generated key results, identifying existing capabilities, gaps, and future developments across technical, operational and architectural domains. The mapping highlighted missing components related to:

- Data access requests, and the role of Principal Investigators (PI) to control data input and output into their project environments compared to the DARE UK model.
- User training and certification.
- Pseudonymisation.

⁴⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trusted_execution_environment

⁴⁸ <https://www.edgeless.systems/products/constellation>

⁴⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Homomorphic_encryption

⁵⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>

⁵¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14192786>

- FAIR Data publishing.

Further validation of the Blueprint by the Drivers was reported in Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1). This report refined the initial Driver requirements into implementation-agnostic descriptions, prioritised and mapped to the SATRE framework, with a focus on interoperability needs within a federated network.

Parallel efforts involving the TRE providers were documented in Deliverable 10.1 (D10.1), the Provider adoption and evaluation report⁵². Key achievements included establishing the TRE Provider Forum, initially comprising 17 organisations from 15 countries. An initial TRE inventory was developed based on a survey, providing critical input for the baseline capabilities and gap analysis. The key challenges for integrating current TREs are related to three main areas, namely: interoperability, training and standardization and data compliance.

Deliverable 16.1 (D16.1), the AAAI for TREs Blueprint, first version, was released in March 2025⁵³. This blueprint builds on the established AARC Blueprint⁵⁴, but proposes four enhancements - account creation, identity vetting, Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) and introduction of an accounting layer.

Deliverable 19.1 (D19.1), Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments, was released in December 2024. This report describes an installable demonstrator of federated sensitive data discovery, built from open source components. It showcased how the Workflow Execution Service (WfExS) backend, combined with a TRE-specific job submission system, could enable TREs to participate in federated networks. The analysis in Section 4.2.1⁵⁵ identified two components missing from the Year one Blueprint architecture, i.e., support for intermediary storage and a minimal disclosure procedure.

Collaboration with the sister projects EOSC-SIESTA and EOSC-TITAN has provided a platform for discussing solutions for secure sensitive data handling. EOSC-SIESTA develops tools for secure analytics, anonymisation, and reproducible cloud-based environments for sensitive data, while EOSC-TITAN has a focus on secure computing platforms.

5.1 Dissemination Activities

Dissemination activities were crucial for presenting these initial results and findings to stakeholders and the broader public, while also gathering feedback.

⁵² <https://zenodo.org/records/14989159>

⁵³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15006945>

⁵⁴ <https://aarc-community.org/architecture/>

⁵⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/14412863>

The First EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop in Helsinki (September 2024) provided a platform for the Drivers to present use cases. Four Drivers presented real-world use cases and highlighted core requirements:

- legal agreements
- encryption in transit
- output-control policies

These requirements were mapped against the DARE UK Blueprint, and gaps identified in the process include support for user certification and training, data-access request workflow, pseudonymization and output approval. Cross WP-alignment sessions laid groundwork for the AAI for TREs Blueprint and examined FAIR workflows versus “closed” TREs, exploring reproducible pipelines and the challenge of federated analytics. Breakout sessions on interoperability, capabilities and governance produced consensus on the need for central registries, a tiered chain-of-trust scheme and template for legal agreements.

An Unconference Session at the EOSC Symposium in Berlin (October 2024), co-hosted with TITAN and SIESTA, presented use cases and showcased EOSC-ENTRUST’s reference architecture for a European network of TREs alongside sister project technologies⁵⁶. Discussions focused on the technical, operational, and governance aspects for federated sensitive data in EOSC.

A Knowledge sharing and collaboration workshop with EuroHPC Sensitive data working groups (Milestone M16⁵⁷) in February 2025, aimed to discuss implementing ENTRUST results in HPC architecture, and identifying follow-up tasks. Key discussions covered various aspects of applying TRE principles to HPC for sensitive data, such as the roles of individuals (PI vs data owner), specific security measures (e.g. memory encryption), strategies for ensuring secure setup, and approaches to threat modelling and penetration testing of TREs. Criteria for labelling an environment as a TRE were discussed, with reference to the SATRE specification. Challenges identified included achieving interoperability across TREs, defining technical requirements for TREs connected to HPC, and managing data transfer, encryption and key management. Legal and regulatory requirements, both in terms of GDPR and country-specific were also discussed.

⁵⁶ <https://eosc-entrust.eu/news/eosc-entrust-joins-other-projects>

⁵⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/14881208>

5.2 Revised Roadmap

[Figure 1](#) illustrates the revised blueprint roadmap. It shows the planned development and evolution of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and the establishment of the European network of TREs. The roadmap is structured across three major phases:

1. Phase 1 - 2024 (Foundation)
2. Phase 2 - 2025 (Co-creation and Validation)
3. Phase 3 - 2026 (Maturity and Continuity)

Overall, the first year established the foundational Blueprint and identified key challenges and gaps through a considerable amount of analysis and validation with the Providers and Drivers. The technical work on AAI and Workflows provided initial blueprints and demonstrators, highlighting further areas of development. Dissemination activities were key in sharing these results and fostering essential dialogue with stakeholders and relevant European initiatives.

Figure 1: Revised blueprint roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST

6. Discussion

The first year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project has seen the completion of the first phase in the Roadmap towards a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis – the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (the Blueprint). This includes a first version of the Blueprint, focusing on the architecture specification for the TRE network, and accompanying first version training material and a machine-readable catalogue of TREs. The Blueprint has been validated by the Drivers and Providers against their requirements and capabilities, and further extended and validated with an AAAI module and an installable demonstrator of federated sensitive data discovery. Importantly, this first phase has both helped mature Driver requirements and helped identify required modifications and extensions to the Blueprint architecture.

In the second phase of the Roadmap, we will extend the Blueprint with operating procedures and interface definitions, while addressing the gaps and additional requirements identified by the Drivers in their analysis of the first version of the Blueprint (see [Section 4.1.2](#)). Importantly, these gaps and requirements cover both the Blueprint architecture, operating procedures, and federation governance structure. The Drivers have also provided a clear recommendation on how to proceed with the next phase of the Blueprint, which is to “focus on four critical areas: architecture, standards, processes, and alignment with EHDS and EOSC on all of these.”⁵⁸ Taking these recommendations to heart, we are closely following ongoing developments within EHDS, EOSC, and other relevant efforts within Europe (see [Section 4.2](#)).

7. Conclusions and Impact

The first year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, corresponding to the first phase in the Roadmap, has seen a prolific production of project results, reflecting the engagement and excitement among the project members. The current report has summarized the work from this first project year and relevant parallel developments within Europe. Based on this work, we have presented a revised Blueprint roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST ([Figure 1](#)). The summaries and revised Roadmap presented here have informed our plans for the next steps in the Blueprint development (see below).

8. Next steps

Engagement across work packages within the ENTRUST project and with external stakeholders ([Section 5.1](#)) has been critical for developing the first version of the Blueprint.

⁵⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/14988869>, p. 39

We aim to continue this engagement in the next project phase, starting with the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop (May 6-7, 2025). The workshop is designed to gather updated expectations of Providers and Drivers, especially in terms of interoperability, and to identify common pain points that could hinder the direction of the Blueprint towards interoperability. We aim to achieve alignment between the different EOSC-ENTRUST WPs, e.g. in terms of the Driver gap analysis, the relationship of the TRE Providers Inventory and the TRE Provider Catalogue, and the AAI and Workflow WP input to the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint.

Following the Requirements and Capabilities Workshop, we will work to address the identified gaps in the Blueprint architecture, and develop first versions of Blueprint operating procedures and interfaces, focusing on the Driver recommendations. We aim to present a draft second version Blueprint architecture and first version operating procedures and interfaces during the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop (to be held September 17-18, 2025). Importantly, the work to develop the Blueprint operating procedures will also require establishing a recommended federation governance structure, as a procedure for joining the federation would require a clear governance structure.

In parallel with revising and extending the Blueprint, we will develop the second version of the TRE Provider Catalogue and develop training material for the Blueprint. The former will be developed in close collaboration with the Providers and their work in gathering data for the Provider Inventory, as this data should ideally inform on each TRE's interoperability services according to the Blueprint architecture. For the training material, we aim to provide this within a framework that can be extended to include the relevant training material required for the established federation itself, such as general safe user training and material related to the general user journey, and specific training material from individual Providers. Importantly, such specific TRE training material should be added to this framework by the individual Providers when joining the federation.